

MODERN INTERPRETATIONS OF THE PHENOMENON OF "SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT"

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Abstract. *In the modern world, one of the most discussed topics by the scientific community, representatives of various fields, economists, political scientists, organizations specializing in defense, ecologists and experts working in other fields is the issue of "sustainable development". After all, it is a fact that does not require proof that positive results cannot be achieved in any field without ensuring sustainable development. Based on these, this article analyzes the essence and content of the phenomenon of sustainable development, as well as reveals the specific aspects of different approaches in this regard.*

Keywords: *sustainable development, goals, criteria, scientific approach, modern world, phenomenon of sustainable development, well-being, society perspective, variability, progressive development, regressive development.*

It can be considered natural that in the last two centuries, most sources have been observing the debates about the emergence and formation of the phenomenon of sustainable development and what are its main indicators.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev expressed the following thoughts on this issue: "Every person who comes to this bright world lives with dreams and hopes, makes various plans for the future, and has good intentions. Likewise, it is natural for every nation to have dreams related to peaceful coexistence, prosperous life, and sustainable development" [1]. Therefore, any nation, state, strengthening its position and influence in the world community, maintaining it, achieving stability of the internal environment, ensuring socio-economic growth are the main means of determining the future of that nation or country.

The general content of the positive results achieved in a particular society is explained by the concept of "sustainable development". Understanding and analyzing the interpretation of this concept given in classical and modern literature is the main direction of our research, so we will talk about the dictionary meaning and origin of the words "sustainability" and "progress".

In the first volume of the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, the phenomena of "stability" and "variability" are compared, and they are defined as follows: "Stability is the characteristic of things and events, and variability is the process of their transition from one state to another." According to the dialectical approach, stability and change are considered in a mutual organic unity, in the form of existing dialectical oppositions" [2].

From these sentences presented in our national dictionary, it can be understood that the concept of sustainability does not acquire a full positive meaning when it comes alone. That is, in some cases, it can be justified to give explanations such as "stagnation", stopping in one place. In the political dictionary "International relations (geopolitics, diplomacy, security)" prepared by Uzbek authors, it is defined as "stability is a concept that represents consistent, even development, socio-economic, political system of society, state sovereignty and territorial integrity"[3]. It should be noted that the second definition has a somewhat positive view, and the owners of this

definition explain sustainability as a phenomenon that means that development continues continuously and without various changes.

The phenomenon of stability is described in detail in "Spirituality: An Explanatory Dictionary of Basic Concepts" published by another Uzbek scientist. According to the definition given in the dictionary, "stability is the existence of peaceful conditions based on the preservation and strengthening of peace, harmony and unity prevailing in society; solidarity between social strata, groups and political parties; a concept that means strong cooperation between the state, public organizations, and citizens" [4]. It is worth noting that in the dictionary, Western and Eastern scientists' views on the phenomenon of stability are compared, and the comparison of its true nature is left to the judgment of the reader.

In the eighth volume of the national encyclopedia, the concept of "development" is described separately and reflects the following content: "Development is a form of development from simple to complex, from bottom to top, its rise. In the literature, progress is often equated with development, in fact, it is a direction of development" [5]. In fact, the concepts of progress and development do not complement each other in content. For example, the concept of development can be justified with negative examples. For example, there are a number of sentences such as the development of the disease, the development of the crisis, which limit the positive tone of the development event. Uzbek philosopher-scientist Professor B. Toraev notes that development will exist in two forms. "Progress (progressive development) and the other is called crisis (regressive development). Due to development, the world is perfected and improved, it takes place in the form of the processes of emergence, complication, growth, renewal, recovery, system formation" [5].

Political scientist, professor Sh Pakhrutdinov in his work "Sustainable development and responsibility of the leader" emphasizes that the phenomenon of development does not always acquire a positive character. According to the scientist, progress and development differ in content. It is not logical to treat these two terms as synonyms. Sh. Pakhrutdinov stated that "Society needs development as a socio-political organism . For example, just as the human body creates a series of demanding needs (food, recreation, biological needs), society also creates various problems based on the essence of the time to ensure its development" [6]. Summarizing the views of the two experts mentioned above, an unanimous conclusion can be reached. The conclusion is that if the development reflects positive features, it serves development, otherwise it can be the reason for the emergence and intensification of crisis.

We have reviewed the definitions available in the local literature above. In order to ensure that the analysis is complete in all respects, there is a need to study some information presented in foreign literature and scientific dictionaries, which allows for a deeper understanding of the concept of sustainable development. In the "Dictionary of Economic Terms" published in Russia, sustainability is defined as follows: "The concept of sustainability does not have a single definition. The most general definition is the Gro Haarlem Brundtland definition, used by the World Commission on Environment and Development: sustainability is "the ability of the present generation to meet its own needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" [7].

The process of formation of approaches to sustainable development goes back to ancient times. Since ancient times, the growth of the population, the existence of certain rules and laws in the use of natural resources, and the issues of regulation of consumption have attracted the

attention of ancient Greek sages. The in-depth study of the term sustainable development and the main approaches took place in recent history, dating back to the second half of the last century. More precisely, it can be observed that research in this direction has been carried out since the 18th century. European Rev. Thomas R. In Malthus's 1798 work entitled "On the Laws of Population", the issue of stability was studied separately and its classic definition was given. According to Malthus's definition, stability is based on economic factors, but religious, cultural and social factors should also form the core of stability. Otherwise, the laws of sustainable development may be broken. At the same time, according to Malthus, it was predicted that "the growth of the population will follow a geometric progression, and the growth of food and production will follow an arithmetic progression, and this will lead to long-term disasters, famines, wars, even revolutions" [8].

Scientific analysis of sustainable development were fully formed in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century. These analysis were mainly reflected in the theoretical and practical views of representatives of the "Club of Rome" and a number of other European scientists. In particular, the Italian economist Aurelio Peccei, at the regular meetings of the "Club of Rome", which he founded, gathers prominent scientists and public figures of the world to analyze the global events taking place in the world and assess the social, economic, cultural and political processes that may occur in the future and has begun to make recommendations on ways to achieve sustainable development. Among them, lectures on factors threatening human development, two world wars, the arms race between countries striving for hegemony, environmental problems arising as a result of wars and other processes and their solutions formed the main content of the club's activities.

During this period, D. Meadows and Y. Randers, who scientifically researched and described in their works the tools that cause the development or decline of human society, should be specially recognized. The work entitled "The Limits of Growth", referred to the public verdict in 1972, aroused great interest in the world community. The general content of this work is that it predicts that the problems arising as a result of the human factor will become anthropogenic and pose a real threat to sustainable development in the future . The authors noted that in the near future, the increase in population, increase in consumption, and excessive use of natural resources will cause a number of irreversible problems.

The second work published by D. Meadows, Beyond the Limits to Growth (1995), was a scholarly publication that once again called the world community to be aware. The statements in this work contain even more extreme views and predictions, according to which the number and scale of global problems will increase in the near future if countries do not develop clear criteria for the use of natural resources, if certain limits are not established, and as a result of population growth and increased consumption. As a result, humanity will face unprecedented economic, social and environmental crises.

In 2003, thirty years after the initial vision of sustainable development, published by the officials of the Club of Rome, a new report was released under the title "The Limits to Growth 30 Years", which shows whether the processes they predicted have been realized or not. The result showed that the ideas expressed in 1972 were fully confirmed thirty years later.

As it can be seen from the given information, the issue of sustainable development has been studied in detail by various experts and shown in various sources in the last half century. However, the origin and author of this term exists - Norwegian statesman and public figure Gru Harlem Brundtland. Brundtland gained the attention of the world community after his lectures

aimed at ensuring peace and stability on the European continent. As a result, in 1983, he was appointed chairman of the Commission on Environmental Development and Protection, a program of the United Nations. In 1987, a report entitled "Our Common Future" was published by this commission, as a result of several years of effective activity of the commission. For the first time in the report, special emphasis was placed on the concept of "Sustainable development" and this concept was proposed for the first time as a separate concept.

The main ideas of the concept of sustainable development developed by the Brundtland Commission are as follows:

The concept of sustainable development:

Understanding the responsibility of meeting the needs of future generations while meeting the needs of the current generation. Considering the priority task of leaving the natural resources available on our planet to future generations;

Ensuring sustainability of economic growth, equal implementation of the principles of social justice for all and protection of the environment.

Cooperation in solving global problems:

New threats facing humanity, mutual cooperation in solving global problems (poverty, air pollution, climate change, etc.);

Further improvement of effective international cooperation mechanisms and strengthening of solidarity in solving existing problems based on their global importance.

Rational use of natural resources:

Increase the efficiency of use of natural resources;

Transition to renewable alternative sources of resources.

Demographic reforms:

Carrying out demographic reforms and managing urbanization processes in the context of population growth;

Special attention should be paid to mutual balancing in the development of urban and rural infrastructure.

It should be noted that during its effective activity, the Brundtland Commission was more effective than other global structures in terms of studying the developments in the world, studying various global problems, and promoting clear and systematic recommendations for their solutions. In order to confirm our opinion, we will consider the general content of the general problems considered by the commission and recommendations for their solution.

First of all, the change of the natural environment as a result of human influence is one of the issues studied separately by the Brundtland Commission. The Commission's conclusions emphasize that environmental pollution and the unreasonable use of natural resources are among the global problems and are at the forefront of problems that may have the most harmful consequences in the future. Since the human factor is at the root of the problem, its solution is directly the responsibility of mankind. In this regard, existing measures, laws created or being created, and modern technologies being developed do not help to fully solve the existing problems. One of the main solutions is to create and implement new approaches and technologies.

From this point of view, concrete solutions have been developed by the commission. They consist of:

the study and implementation of their renewable properties in the use of natural resources has a positive effect on environmental stability;

Studying the ecological consequences of anthropogenic hazards caused by the human factor, giving legal, social, political and spiritual assessment to it, regularly informing the public, analyzing it with the participation of experts are among the primary mechanisms of environmental protection;

states, governments, large industrial facilities, international organizations, non-governmental and non-profit organizations, citizens, establishing systems of self-control and mutual restraint are the next means of environmental protection;

Another important factor is the development of technologies for efficient use of resources in order to rationally use nature and save natural resources.

One of the global issues that was separately studied by the Brundtland Commission was the economic development of all regions.

It seems impossible for all regions on our planet to develop equally, but if humanity really wants to, it can be done. In this regard, it is necessary to develop modern principles of the concept of sustainable development and improve them based on the requirements of the time.

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